

A Photochemical Route to Oxidative Phenol Coupling[†]

TARASANKAR PAL* and ANJALI PAL

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur-721 302

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Pummerer's ketone (2), *o,o*-coupled dimer (3), the *ortho*-coupled tetramer (6a) and the usual reductive dimer, viz. benzopinacol (7) have been obtained by photoirradiating *p*-cresol in presence of benzophenone in acetone medium under nitrogen atmosphere. Under the same condition 2-naphthol gives 1,1'-bi-2-naphthol (9) as the sole isolable product. The major advantage of this process has been the least polymerisation owing to the introduction of a mild organic oxidant.

THE postulation¹ of the biogenetic theory of oxidative phenol coupling of phenolic precursors as an obligatory step in the cellular synthesis of a wide variety of natural polyphenolics has generated considerable interest among the organic chemists^{2,3} for mimicking the proposed natural process in the laboratory. Scientists, however, so far have been confined to the usual inorganic^{1,4,5} or bioinorganic⁶ reagents most of them being either simple compounds or complexes of transition metals. But inorganic reagents in many cases, when tried for the synthesis of a number of natural derivatives, led to extensive polymerisation⁴. Moreover, the use of some of those reagents in aqueous alkaline condition brings about additional unwanted transformations. In addition to these, utilisation of the heterogeneous media for the reaction evidently causes poor yield⁷ of the desired products. Thus to control the reaction at the desired step in obtaining selective products, we motivated ourselves in search of a mild organic reagent.

The phenol coupling reaction seems to involve oxidation of phenoxide ion, produced in an alkaline medium, through electron transfer process producing phenoxyl radical which in turn dimerises. Our principal idea was to investigate whether it is possible to generate this radical by direct hydrogen abstraction from phenol using suitable organic moiety especially the organic free radicals.

Photoinitiated ketyl radical (1) generation (Scheme 1) from benzophenone through hydrogen abstraction from solvents like alcohols or amines⁸

suggests the use of similar reagents in phenol coupling process. In case it happens, a new chapter will be opened dealing with controllable polymerisation under a neutral, mild and homogeneous condition in presence of an organic reagent. The present paper explores the scope of the new synthetic method and reports the hitherto unknown investigations on *p*-cresol and 2-naphthol.

Results and Discussion

Oxidation of *p*-cresol with alkaline $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$ was first studied by Pummerer *et al.*⁹ and later by Barton *et al.*⁹ when they reported the isolation of three compounds and assigned their structures as 2, 3 and 4 on the basis of some preliminary spectral (mainly uv and ir) and chemical evidences.

In course of reinvestigation of the above reaction, Majumder and Kundu¹⁰ isolated two more compounds, in addition to those three, and assigned structures their as 5 and 6a with ~20% loss in the starting material due to polymerisation.

This paper deals with the isolation of 2, 3 and 6a by photoillumination of *p*-cresol in acetone in presence of benzophenone under N_2 atmosphere.

Another phenolic product, though produced in a considerable amount (0.19 g), remained uncharacterised because it could not be isolated in the pure state. Benzophenone produced benzopinacol (7) through reductive coupling, as expected, and it was confirmed from the isolation of 7 from the reaction mixture. No benzhydrol (8) was formed in this case. In this process, the formation of 3 in a greater extent than 2 (which was the major product in $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$ oxidation) may provide additional insights into the coupling process which can serve as an useful guide for biomimetic synthesis of appropriate phenolic natural product.

All the products were authenticated from the direct comparison (co-tlc, co-ir and m.m.p.) with synthetic samples¹⁰ and also from ¹H nmr spectra (Table 1).

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TABLE 1—PHYSICAL CONSTANTS AND ¹H NMR SPECTRAL DATA^a OF 2, 3, 6b, 7 AND THAT^b OF 9

Compd.	m.p. (°C)	δ ^a
2	125	1.49(3H, s), 2.24(3H, s), 4.60(1H, m), 2.80(2H, doublet of ABq), 5.82(1H, d, J 10 Hz), 6.35(1H, dd, J ₁ 10 Hz, J ₂ 2.5 Hz), 6.60(1H, d, J 10 Hz), 6.86(1H, d, J 10 Hz), 6.90(1H, d, J 2.5 Hz)
3	153	2.25(6H, s), 5.75(2H, s), 6.83(2H, dd, J ₁ 10 Hz, J ₂ 2.5 Hz), 6.93(2H, d, J 10 Hz), 7.05(2H, d, J 2.5 Hz)
6b	171	1.72(6H, s), 2.08 (6H, s), 2.36(12H, s), 7.25–7.50 (10H, m)
7	186	2.80(2H, s), 6.9–7.2 (20H, m)
9	216	7.2–8.0 (12H, m), 8.7 (2H, disappeared on deuteration)

^aSpectra were run: in CDCl₃ for 2, 3, 6b and 7, in DMSO-d₆ + CDCl₃ for 9.

2-Naphthol gave the only isolable dimer 1,1'-bi-2-naphthol (9) when subjected to photo-oxidation with benzophenone in acetone medium, under the same reaction condition as that employed for *p*-cresol where one obtains a number of products. The identity of the compound with that obtained by FeCl₃ oxidation¹¹ of 2-naphthol was confirmed by direct comparison (co-tlc, co-ir and m.m.p.). Although the overall yield of the products was small, the inhibition of polymerisation was verified

by the almost complete recovery of the unconverted starting materials in both the cases.

Experimental

The ¹H nmr spectra were recorded on a Varian CFT-20 instrument operating at 80 MHz and ir spectra on a Beckman 20 spectrophotometer. Silica gel (60–100 mesh) was used for column chromatography and silica gel G for tlc. All the analytical samples were routinely dried over P₂O₅ at 80° for 24 h under reduced pressure and the purity was tested by tlc and mass spectrometry. Petrol used had b.p. 60–80°.

Photoirradiation of *p*-cresol and benzophenone in a mixture: *p*-Cresol (2.0 g) was dissolved in acetone (50 ml), nitrogen was bubbled through the solution and then benzophenone (3.5 g) was added. The reaction mixture was irradiated with visible light for 18 h. Solvent was then evaporated in a rotavap. Tlc analysis of the reaction mixture when compared with authentic compounds 2, 3, 4, 5, 6a (obtained from the hydrolysis of 6b by methanolic Na₂CO₃) and 7, showed that 2, 3 and 6a were produced as the usual coupled products of *p*-cresol with *in situ* reduction of benzophenone to 7.

Column chromatographic separation of the reaction mixture over silica gel afforded benzophenone (3.08 g) and 7 (0.28 g) in 100 : 1 petrol–EtOAc eluate. Unconverted *p*-cresol (1.6 g) was collected in 50 : 1 petrol–EtOAc fraction. The other products, viz. 2 (0.02 g) and 3 (0.05 g) were isolated in 20 : 1 and 10 : 1 petrol–EtOAc eluate respectively. The compound 6a (isolated in the latter fractions of 10 : 1 and early fractions of 5 : 1 petrol–EtOAc) was, however, isolated in pure state as in the acetate form 6b (0.06 g). Physical and spectroscopic data of the compounds (Table 1) are in consistence with those of the authentic samples obtained from K₃[Fe(CN)₆] oxidation of *p*-cresol¹⁰.

Photoirradiation of 2-naphthol in presence of benzophenone under the same condition: 2-Naphthol (3.0 g) in acetone (50 ml) in nitrogen atmosphere was allowed to react with benzophenone (3.5 g) maintaining the identical condition as in the case of *p*-cresol. Chromatographic separation of the reaction mixture in silica gel afforded unconverted benzophenone (3.12 g) and benzopinacol (7; 0.30 g) in 100 : 1 petrol–EtOAc eluate followed by unconverted 2-naphthol (2.9 g) in 20 : 1 petrol–EtOAc fraction. The product 1,1'-bi-2-naphthol (9; 0.08 g) was collected in the petrol–EtOAc 10 : 1 eluate as the only isolable product. The physical constants and spectroscopic data of 9 are in conformity with those of authentic 1,1'-bi-2-naphthol obtained by FeCl₃ method (Table 1).

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